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List of abbreviations

CDTI	The Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology
FFG	The Austrian Research Promotion Agency
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Innoviris	Institute for the promotion of research and innovation in Brussels capital region
PRO-Ethics	Participatory Real-Life Experiments in Research and Innovation Funding Organisations on Ethics
R&D	Research and Development
R&D&I	Research and Development and Innovation
RCL	The Research Council of Lithuania
RCN	The Research Council of Norway
RFO	Research and Innovation Funding Organisation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
UEFISCDI	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research and Innovation Funding in Romania
VDE	Association for Electrical, Electronic and Information Technologies
VDI	Association of German Engineers
VDI/VDE-IT	VDI/VDE – Innovation + Technology
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report, *Synthesis Report on the Pilots' Experiences*, presents the main findings from the critical examination of the pilot experiences of the second pilot phase of the PRO-Ethics project. It covers points of departure, processes and results, identifying the most important barriers, drivers and good practices, and provides recommendations that have emerged during the experimental ethical implementation of participatory processes in the activities of six research funding organisations (RFOs) in six different countries conducting the pilot project: CDTI, FFG, Innoviris, RCN, UEFISCDI, and VDI/VDE-IT.

The PRO-Ethics project's main goal is to elaborate an ethics framework with principles, guidelines, assessment criteria, good practices and proposals on regulatory environments on how citizen engagement can be properly put in place while maintaining ethical principles of fairness, transparency, gender equality, privacy and sustainability. This report is undertaken within PRO-Ethics WP3 – “Cross pilots learning on the practical implementation of the ethics framework and guidelines”, whose main goal is to facilitate the sharing and mutual-learning from experiences across the piloting processes, as well as to enable qualified feedback on the ethics framework for the purpose of its further improvement.

The six organisations that carried out participatory pilot projects in the context of the project were: the Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology (CDTI) in Spain, The Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG), the Institute for the promotion of research and innovation in Brussels Capital Region (Innoviris), The Research Council of Norway (RCN), The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research and Innovation Funding in Romania (UEFISCDI), and the Association for Electrical, Electronic and Information Technologies/Association of German Engineers + Innovation + Technology (VDE/VDI-IT) in Germany.

The second phase of piloting started as early as August 2021 and, at the time of this report, one pilot is still carrying out activities. This report builds on the data collected between November 2021 and April 2023, from different sources across WP3 and WP2, “Testing the ethics framework in real life pilots”. These include:

- ▶ RFO capacity building event held online in November 2021
- ▶ 2nd and 3rd cross-learning workshops, held respectively online in April 2022 and in Copenhagen in March 2023, reported in *D3.3 Report on Cross-Pilot Workshop Activities*
- ▶ Pilot stories collected between February 2021 and April 2023, compiled in *D3.4 Compilation of the Ethics Narrative in Real-Life Experiences*
- ▶ Pilot activity reports included in *D2.4 Reports on Pilot II Results*
- ▶ Workshop held in November 2022 in Brussels

This document details the results of T3.5, *Analysis, Evaluation and Synthesis of Pilot Experiences*, and presents the pilots' processes and results, the most common barriers and drivers of implementation, highlights some of the good practices that have emerged from the processes, and draws some final recommendations about the potential strategies and approaches for applying participatory activities in organisations similar to the ones undertaking the experiments.

Lessons learned from the pilots' experiments:

- 1) A collaborative process is key from the start: Engaging stakeholders from the beginning fosters a sense of ownership and commitment and helps in minimising bias by involving a range of perspectives which in turn facilitates sustained interest and support for the process throughout.
- 2) Plan realistically (and ahead): Because RFOs are dependent on political decision makers that provide budgets for funding programmes and co-create the R&D agenda, it is important to be realistic regarding the goals of the project, keeping in mind also the availability of resources.
- 3) Be flexible – learn and adjust along the way: As many organisations felt, while operating with limited time and budget, a continuous adjustment of ambitions and expectations at all stages of the process is necessary for a successful implementation of the plan.
- 4) Communication is not engagement: Participatory approaches demand a higher level of engagement than communication alone can provide. While clear and honest communication throughout the process is crucial, being engaged and effectively participating goes beyond just receiving information.
- 5) Be aware of constant ethical checks throughout: A successful participatory approach must attend to constant ethical checks throughout the process. Participatory processes in the context of RFOs mean constant interaction. Therefore, different ethical issues may need to be tackled and negotiated at different stages.
- 6) Change of culture is long-term: Change of organisational culture need a long time, extended effort, and continuous organisational uptake. Effective organisational change and the embrace of a collaborative approach heavily rely on the support provided by the institution and its external dependencies.

Introduction

This *Synthesis Report on the Pilots' Experiences* presents the main findings from the critical examination of the PRO-Ethics pilot experiences of the second pilot phase. It details the learnings that have emerged during the experimental ethical implementation of participatory processes in the activities of six research funding organisations (RFOs) in six different countries conducting the pilot project: CDTI in Spain, FFG in Austria, Innoviris in Belgium/Brussels Capital Region, RCN in Norway, UEFISCDI in Romania, and VDI/VDE-IT in Germany.

The report is divided in two parts: The first looks at the organisations themselves and outlines initial points of departure for each, giving context in terms of processes and (intended) results. The second part looks at the implementation processes in greater detail, identifying the most important barriers, drivers and good practices. From these, the report in its conclusion provides recommendations for the implementation of participatory engagement in the activities of research funding organisations.

The PRO-Ethics project's main goal is to elaborate an ethics framework with principles, guidelines, assessment criteria, good practices and proposals on regulatory environments on how citizen engagement can be properly put in place while maintaining ethical principles of fairness, transparency, gender equality, privacy and sustainability. This report was developed as part of WP3 "Cross pilots learning on the practical implementation of the ethics framework and guidelines", aimed at facilitating the mutual exchange of experiences across the piloting processes, as well as to enable qualified feedback on the Ethics Framework to the purpose of its further improvement. While the first four pilots of phase I, implemented at the start of the project, offered valuable insights that informed the initial version of the framework, i.e., *D1.4 Ethics Framework 0.1 and Guidelines*, the current deliverable focuses on the second pilot phase, where the pilot experiences involved testing and refining the draft ethics framework.

At the time of this reporting, the final version of the ethics framework (*D5.2 Ethics Framework 1.0 and D5.3 Practical Guidelines and Criteria*) has been completed. The results of this deliverable will be used in the dissemination of the project outcomes.

The second phase of piloting started as early as August 2021 and, at the time of this report, one pilot is still carrying out activities. This report builds on the data collected between November 2021 and April 2023, from different sources across WP3 and WP2 "Testing the ethics framework in real life pilots". These include:

- ▶ RFO capacity building event held online in November 2021
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- ▶ Workshop held in November 2022 in Brussels

This document details the results of T3.5, *Analysis, Evaluation and Synthesis of Pilot Experiences* and presents the pilots' processes and results, the most common barriers and drivers of implementation,

highlights some of the good practices that have emerged from the processes and draws some final recommendations about the potential strategies and approaches for applying participatory activities in organisations similar to the ones undertaking the experiments.

Methodology

The data collected across WP2 and WP3 was structured and systematised following the goal of the task: a synthetic and final evaluation of the pilots' experiments. The focus was on the experiences as reported by the pilot leads at several settings and formats (online and in-person workshops, first-hand free narratives, templates with pre-given categories/questions), particularly, the barriers and drivers they have encountered throughout the process, as well as the good practices to overcome some of the barriers and to enable some of the drivers. Furthermore, a thematic analysis was undertaken, following a qualitative content analysis, where the main themes of the best practices across pilots emerged in order to summarise the experiences and offer recommendations.

Implementation organisations: points of departure, processes and results

The following chapter is a summarised version from the more detailed overview of the pilots' processes and results provided in *D2.4 Reports on Pilot II Results* (primary author Stefanie Schuerz). For first-hand accounts and reflections on the piloting experiences by the pilot leads, refer to *D3.4 Compilation of the Ethics Narrative in Real-Life Experiences*.

CDTI: Evaluation of the Social Impact of the NEOTEC Programme

Organisation and point of departure

CDTI is a Spanish public organisation for technology development and innovation answering to the Ministry of Science and Innovation. CDTI manages the Neotec funding programme, which provides grants for New Technology-Based Firms (NTBs) to carry out projects that require the use of technologies or knowledge developed from research activities as well as a viable business plan. The objective of Neotec is to foster the transfer of knowledge from research organisations or expert teams to industry, seeing NTBs as a viable instrument to take scientific and technological progress generated in laboratories into the market, and in turn into society. Due to its multiple social implications, the Neotec programme has been selected as a pilot to test new open evaluation approaches based on the participation of programme beneficiaries.

To this end, CDTI implemented 5 focus groups and a total of 30 interviews with various stakeholders, followed by an in-depth analysis of the gathered material. The main goal of the participatory activities was to develop an evaluation methodology including evaluation criteria for measuring the social impact of RDI projects funded by Neotec. Further on, CDTI aims to apply the outcome of the participatory exercise in evaluating other internal funding programmes, as well as disseminating it within its sphere of influence – mainly, regional innovation agencies and other public bodies in charge of RDI policy in Spain and the European evaluation community.

Process and results

A first focus group was conducted with CDTI administrative management to review and validate the structure, processes and goals of the logic model for the pilot. In this context, expert inputs on qualitative evaluation methodology were also provided, which had been hired externally. The discussion focused on which questions should be answered through the evaluation, identification of relevant stakeholders to be involved in the evaluation, and relevant criteria for selecting beneficiaries of the programme for the exploratory stage of the evaluation. The workshop was perceived as highly valuable and motivating and led to three programme managers joining the evaluation team.

This workshop was followed by interviews with various experts and stakeholders, including: “social stakeholders”, i.e., umbrella organizations representing both sources of R&I initiatives and prospective users of innovations; external programme managers from regional innovation agencies; Neotec programme beneficiaries and consultancy firms giving support to tech start-ups. The semi-structured interviews aimed at further exploring what questions should be covered by the evaluation and which societal stakeholders would be relevant to include in the evaluation process. The CDTI team received positive feedback from interview participants, who provided complementary perspectives on the Neotec programme.

Based on the inputs provided in these interviews, CDTI developed and pre-tested an online questionnaire, which was sent out to more than 1.300 companies who had been applying for Neotec funding between 2018 and 2022, of which 31% completed all questions. The questionnaire approached the impact of individual projects in relation to the SDGs (UN Sustainable Development Goals), with responses showing a strong positive correlation with health and quality of life, reducing the carbon footprint, and climate change mitigation in this self-assessment. While a positive relation with the digital divide was still quite pronounced, social inequality, quality education, poverty and social inclusion, and gender equality were much less in focus of Neotec-funded projects.

The second stage of the pilot included the actual evaluation of the social impact of projects funded through the Neotec programme. Based on the collected information from all activities of the exploratory phase, CDTI managed to define new evaluation questions that open the scope of the project evaluation towards the assessment of social impact that could also be applied in the evaluation of other programs in the future.

FFG: Citizen Participation in Call Topic Definition

Organisation and point of departure

FFG is the Austrian national funding agency for applied and industrial research and innovation and manages funding mostly provided by different ministries and other public institutions. For several years, the FFG R&I funding programmes *benefit* and *AAL* have focused on combining pressing issues of demographic change with the development of useful ICT-based solutions. The programmes are now evolving into a new funding topic called “Digital Solutions for People and Society”. Under the umbrella of this new theme, the aim of the FFG pilot is to explore relevant subtopics that combine health topics, climate change and demographic change, while also taking into consideration the possibilities that information and communication technologies offer. As part of this pilot, FFG involved citizens in the definition of call topics through a multi-step process: expert interviews, a validation workshop and an online survey.

Process and results

FFG does not usually perform broader citizen engagement processes when defining call topics, so this was a new experience for the team. First, they needed to secure budget and commitment and find a suitable funding scheme for this new participatory process. To this end, ministry partners needed to be onboarded throughout 2021. FFG designed and then started implementing the multi-step process to investigate relevant dimensions of climate change, health, and demographic change, in connection with new technologies.

The separate activities had individual goals and built on each other. The first exploration phase included selected stakeholders and experts through 13 semi-structured interviews in early 2022. Insights gained there were analysed in May and June 2022. In June 2022, at the validation workshop, the results and insights from the interviews were discussed and the participants contributed with their expertise on the nexus of climate change, health and technology. The main activity of the workshop was a “brainwalk” where participants walked between four stations and discussed with the host of that station on a specific topic. Based on the inputs collected in the first two steps, a questionnaire was developed, consisting of both closed and open questions, and aimed at collecting inputs on the experiences and expectations of citizens regarding the interrelation between climate change, health, and RDI funding

projects with the survey being open from the end of June until mid-August 2022. The activity led to abundant and rich responses from participants with a total of 123 completed surveys. In December 2022, FFG launched the first funding call based on the results of the different stages of the process. A second call is planned to follow at the end of 2023. In addition, FFG plans to hold a second validation workshop to deepen insight into selected thematically relevant aspects. The results from all pilot activities will also be analysed to feed into a study where the FFG will report on the pilot and summarise the received input.

Innoviris: Citizen Participation in Thematic Definition of Programme Calls

Organisation and point of departure

Innoviris is a public organization that funds and supports research and innovation in the Brussels Capital Region (BCR) and (co-)finances R&I projects in companies, research centers, and the non-profit and public sector. The pilot aimed to find a suitable design and method for engaging a broad cut of the population living in the Brussels Capital Region and identify challenges that should be addressed through funding, via its policy-oriented research programme Prospective Research. As a first step, the team at Innoviris conducted desk research to identify concrete challenges from the Regional Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisations⁵ (RIS3), which is distilled from political plans, megatrends, data analyses, etc. This is the typical procedure for call topics at Innoviris. This was followed by a consultation with regional public actors and centers of expertise with knowledge on regional challenges, implemented through an online questionnaire collecting inputs on the challenges identified through the desk research. Based on this, Innoviris developed and conducted an open online survey with residents of the BCR. Finally, two citizen ateliers were organized in person, where residents discussed different urban challenges among themselves and with experts.

Process and results

The pilot team at Innoviris consisted of an internal task force composed of the programme manager, internal advisors, team leaders and policy and monitoring experts. The team first conducted desk research to identify the challenges from local and regional documents, such as RIS3 and other regional development strategies. This was followed by a consultation of regional public actors and centers of expertise with knowledge on regional challenges. Nineteen actors within the Innoviris network were approached via an online questionnaire. Six questionnaires were returned with suggestions for key research themes linked to local challenges framed within the region's smart specialisation domains.

Building on these inputs, the team developed an online survey for citizens using a citizen participation tool to engage citizens in topic prioritisation in June 2022. Innoviris chose to limit this exploration to the five most important challenges identified by the expert consultation, which were presented on the platform with a short description in different languages: 1) social inequality and poverty – climate change as an accelerator; 2) polarisation of society; 3) the real estate market – available and affordable space; 4) well-being in a security society; 5) media and society. The participants were asked to choose the most important challenge facing the region in the next 20 years. Through an open question, respondents could also name an additional challenge not suggested above.

Based on the inputs provided by 59 survey participants, Innoviris implemented two citizen ateliers, 3-4 hours each on the evenings of 30 June and 6 July 2022. The first workshop was designed as a reverse science café. Out of 23 confirmed participants, only 10 attended. Citizens were split into different

thematic working groups to discuss subthemes with which citizens had an affinity. The goal of this workshop was to initiate a public dialogue involving citizens and representatives of different RRI programmes or policy processes. The group discussions result in recommendations briefly summarised in writing. The second citizen atelier was designed as a scenario workshop, which was intended as a follow-up activity to the previous atelier. While the same participants were invited, only 3 took part. The scenario at the center of the activity was intended as a first scoping of a potential future call. This scenario was discussed by the participants. While participation in these activities was disappointing, even though compensation was offered, the outcome of these workshops helped Innoviris redefine the focus of the call and develop relevant research questions.

RCN: Citizen Participation Learning Hub

Organisation and point of departure

RCN is a Norwegian government agency funding both basic and applied research and innovation. The RCN pilot has been carried out in close cooperation with RCL, which fulfils a similar role funding R&D in Lithuania. The main goal of the pilot was to develop the Involve Hub as a community of practice for mutual exchange on ethical dilemmas and other aspects of citizens participation in scientific knowledge production. Thematically, these activities aimed at 1) addressing potential ethical challenges of citizen involvement in research, 2) inviting inputs for developing the Ethics Framework, and 3) collecting feedback on how the Research Council can work better with regards to ethical citizen involvement. The Involve Hub builds on former and ongoing experiences with participatory activities at RCN, including some carried out in collaboration with RCL. While these were carried out without a special focus on research ethics or research integrity, the Involve Hub entails a network of key stakeholders to share knowledge, discuss challenges and identify solutions related to ethical participation in R&I. The Hub was organized in three online gatherings during the period August 2022 to January 2023, as well as two preliminary integrating workshops prior to the Hub-gatherings (on 28 January and 27 April).

Process and results

The three gatherings engaged a relatively stable group of participants. The first workshop kicked off the process with a focus on ethical challenges faced when citizens are involved in research. It included an expert introduction as well as input from three researchers with experience in citizen involvement. There were 20 participants in total. In the course of the workshop, the various inputs highlighted important issues and reflections on the ethics of citizen participation. The second workshop with 17 participants built on the learnings of the first event and was dedicated to discussing the Ethics Framework. Concrete feedback on the Ethics Framework was received, namely, the value of the Framework beyond R&I projects and processes was emphasised, as well as the importance of giving guidance on the inclusion of vulnerable groups and securing their representation, and the value of compensation of participants. The third workshop focused on RCN's work on ethics and citizen involvement. These inputs also laid out how the Ethics Framework will be integrated in RCN's work on ethics. RCN received some very concrete and useful input and suggestions from the participants, which will be considered for further work at the Research Council. In parallel to these Hub meetings, RCN tried to establish an online platform to develop and strengthen the community of practice beyond the three gatherings. However, as use of the platform did not gain lasting momentum, this channel of communication was discontinued after several months. The main achievements of pilot activities are the knowledge exchange between the participants and the broadening of the perspectives of the involved stakeholders as they contributed

with their expertise. The Hub activity created a systemic perspective on the changes needed to embark on the mandate of ethics of involvement.

UEFISCDI: Citizen Participation in the National R&D Strategy 2021-2027

Organisation and point of departure

UEFISCDI is a national Romanian research funding agency that has contributed to the development of the National Research, Innovation and Smart Specialisation Strategy 2022-2027. In the context of the pilot activities, UEFISCDI decided to employ a participatory approach to refine the 2022-2027 Romanian National Agenda for Research by engaging citizens in validating and enriching the proposed thematic priorities. The Strategic Research Agenda is a list of societal challenges and leading questions elaborated through a lengthy process with experts and public bodies. The two citizen engagement activities implemented by UEFISCDI were thus aimed at aligning the experts and public authorities' views with the needs and experiences of citizens.

The goal of this pilot was to test if such an endeavor, i.e., involving citizens in the development of national, strategic documents and instruments, was possible. Another aim was to explore if citizens could engage and understand research topics well enough to meaningfully contribute to the process of refining, enriching or just validating the research questions, and thus whether this approach was a viable strategy to potentially repeat in the future. The citizen working groups were asked to add, rephrase or confirm what experts had elaborated based on their own views, beliefs, interests and needs. As this was an initial experiment, the project team could not guarantee that participant inputs would be included in the final official document, as the findings of the workshop were presented to the official authorities merely as a suggestion. Nevertheless, some of the inputs were indeed integrated in the final agenda.

Process and results

The pilot activity at UEFISCDI was mostly a novelty since the types of stakeholders usually engaged in the processes of the RFO are experts, researchers, policymakers, and business actors. The involvement of citizens in commenting and refining the national research agenda, took place in the context of two identical workshops on 13 May and 20 May 2022, held as physical events. Both workshops involved 30 citizens each, with 60 individuals participating in total. The participants were citizens selected in such a manner as to provide some variety regarding their age, gender, level of education and geographic distribution between rural and urban areas. The recruitment process was commissioned to a recruitment company, as UEFISCDI decided there were not sufficient resources nor expertise to recruit a representative sample internally. UEFISCDI provided a set of criteria to the recruitment company for sampling participants. Participants received compensation in the form of a voucher provided by the recruitment company according to its internal compensation system. Some of the inputs were integrated in the final agenda.

VDE/VDI - IT: Engaging Citizens in Project Evaluation and Implementation

Organisation and point of departure

VDI/VDE-IT works closely with the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research. The pilot of VDI/VDE-IT originated from this cooperation and was designed to accompany a funding call on technological solutions to support informal caregivers. The pilot set up a citizen advisory board

(henceforth CAB), which participated in the proposal evaluation and selection of suitable projects. The members of the CAB are also involved as mentors during the implementation of the innovation projects at the time of writing of this report. The CAB consists of people who provide or have provided informal care to relatives, friends or acquaintances and are therefore regarded as lay experts in the field of informal care. The pilot thus enables informal caregivers to have a direct impact on the project selection and execution processes as well as the final product that is designed to support informal caregiving. In addition, their involvement would give CAB members an insight into the process of funding and developing technologies.

Process and results

The CAB had its inaugural online meeting on August 24, 2021, where they familiarised themselves with each other and gained an understanding of the pilot's objectives and processes. It provided a platform for exchanging experiences, discussing the specific needs of informal caregivers, and expressing expectations for the pilot. In September 2021, the CAB received an online briefing on the proposal evaluation and selection process employed by VDI/VDE-IT. The CAB members were assigned specific proposals to evaluate, while pilot participants had access to all proposals in both simplified and comprehensive scientific versions. The board members individually rated project drafts online, considering both versions of the proposals. In October 2021, the CAB discussed online proposal ratings and made recommendations for funding. The CAB also elected two spokespeople to represent them in the scientific board meeting for the final funding decision. In November 2021, the final selection session occurred, where the scientific panel collaborated with the chosen CAB representatives to determine the conclusive selection of project proposals. The CAB met again in December 2021 for a joint reflection on past activities, presentation of the selected projects, and the selection of mentors for the upcoming research phase. Throughout 2022, CAB members engaged in various activities, including kick-off meetings, practical sessions, and networking events. In March 2023, the CAB had its first in-person meeting to reflect on the project's progress, encompassing project selection, mentoring, and the overall satisfaction of CAB members with the pilot.

Implementation processes: barriers, drivers and good practices

This chapter outlines the main barriers, drivers and good practices identified during the piloting of participatory processes in the six RFOs of the PRO-Ethics consortium. Each section starts out by discussing the most prevalent or notable examples of each category.

Barriers

There were various barriers faced by the different pilots in their efforts to engage citizens in participatory processes. While some challenges are specific to the pilot and the RFO leading it, several common traits can be listed. In the first place, it seems that there was in several engagement activities a low response rate. Some pilots struggled to find the desirable number of participants. The reasons given for this are diverse, ranging from bad timing, being unable to convey a clear message, wrong choice of communication channels and/or engagement formats, struggle with engaging with potential multipliers for disseminating the calls, language barriers, lack of accessibility, digital illiteracy, etc. Another common challenge was lack of desired representativeness in participation; ensuring a heterogeneous and representative sample of the broad population proved to be difficult across pilots. Respondents to surveys or workshop participants were often skewed in relation to the broader population, with biases towards higher education and specific age groups. Inadequate messaging, insufficient planning when determining the right time to launch campaigns/activities, and missing the right incentives were some of the causes which hindered the recruitment and engagement efforts of diverse target groups. Moreover, some RFOs faced difficulties due to a lack of established procedures and experience in incorporating participatory engagement in their own organisational contexts. Other common barriers included managing expectations both internally and from the participants, compensation issues, and engaging external stakeholders.

In specific, the RFO partners of PRO-Ethics outlined the following barriers encountered in the implementation of their respective pilot.

CDTI

- ▶ Engaging stakeholders out of the traditional scope of the programme was challenging as they were not familiarised with the programme.
- ▶ The response rate of the survey was only 31%. Since Neotec has been designed according to technological and economic goals, the surveyed participants (applicants to the programme) could have the perception that social impact was beyond the scope of their projects, being more reluctant to answer it.

FFG

- ▶ Designing a method from scratch where citizens provide sufficient and qualified input to be taken into consideration by experts/researchers was a challenge.
- ▶ Communicating clearly to citizens the benefits of their interaction throughout the participatory process – why they should participate and what is the value in it for them – proved to be challenging.

- ▶ Reservations about the sufficient number of participants in the workshop and respondents in the survey and the overall right approach to participatory processes were also voiced by FFG.
- ▶ Even though several multiplier organisations initially showed interest in supporting the project, this support never materialised. Reasons for this may be privacy concerns and missing buy-in from the top management, limited time and resources at these organisations, and also potential rivalry regarding the engagement of available citizens.
- ▶ The self-selection of participants for the validation workshop and the citizen survey meant that there was a strong bias in participants towards middle-aged women with higher education.
- ▶ While the validation workshop was advertised through FFG channels before the conference, on-site visibility was limited, and the number of participants remained below the desired number.

Innoviris

- ▶ A challenge lay in negotiating the degree of influence granted to citizens and other stakeholders regarding both the definition of and final decision on call topics, and to manage the expectations of political decision-makers.
- ▶ Multiplier organisations with access to the intended target groups did not seem to disseminate the online survey as expected.
- ▶ The respondents of the online survey were over 95% higher educated, thus not representative of the population of the Brussels Capital Region. One of the possible reasons was that June is a busy month of the year with many participatory initiatives going on simultaneously.
- ▶ Due to budget and time constraints, the survey was only published in Dutch, French and English (the three official languages of the BCR), while recruitment for the citizen panel was only done in Dutch and French. This excluded a considerable part of the population of the BCR, while it may have deterred others who feel less secure or fluent in any of these languages.
- ▶ While Innoviris tried to involve a broad sample of the population via representative sampling, limitations in time and funding meant the team could not implement this approach as needed and had little leeway to reflect on and adjust its approach.
- ▶ While Innoviris had previously been successful with online recruitment approaches, the social media campaign had to be taken offline after only a few days because some of the contents of the campaign (namely the statements) were deemed too sensitive in the current political climate.
- ▶ Despite Innoviris engaging a professional participant recruitment company to maximise the chances of success, by having to rely on street-sourcing turnout was negatively impacted. In particular, it became apparent that certain groups were less likely to respond to a street survey, making it extremely difficult to reach citizens over the age of 45, for instance.
- ▶ Participants recruited via street-sourcing were less intrinsically motivated (something that has been confirmed in other recruitment campaigns by the recruitment company) and thus more likely to discontinue their involvement than citizens recruited through other methods, in particular online campaigns.
- ▶ Even though compensation was offered, most of the confirmed participants did not attend the workshops.

RCN

- ▶ Involving a broader spectrum of external stakeholders/participants proved to be challenging, especially regarding representatives of the private/industry sector.

- ▶ A lack of experience and expertise in ethical engagement and participatory processes at the organisational level, as well as a certain top-down approach were seen as a challenge.
- ▶ While at least one of the Hub gatherings was intended to be held in person, there were not enough registrations beforehand to warrant this effort, which led RCN to postpone and hold the final workshop online as well. Even though RCN offered to cover travel costs, it was hard for many participants to take the extra time to attend in person.
- ▶ The online engagement format, established to develop and strengthen the community beyond the three gatherings, could not be sustainably implemented resulting in a limited number of participants using the tool to provide additional feedback. This was partly due to technical issues, which delayed the availability of the infrastructure until the final stages of the process. Moreover, the platform was perceived as insufficiently accessible, which was exacerbated by participants' time constraints and a lack of incentives to maintain ongoing communication through the platform.
- ▶ In the first workshop, not enough time was allocated for discussion, which led to some attendees acting more as passive observers than active participants.

UEFISCDI

- ▶ While the engagement format chosen by UEFISCDI was accessible, allowing for a meaningful and equal interaction between the participants, it was quite resource intense. As a consequence, only two workshops could be organised, involving a total of 60 citizens.

VDE/VDI-IT

- ▶ Finding out the right recruitment method is particularly challenging when reaching out to vulnerable groups such as informal caregivers, as they could be hindered by different barriers to participation.
- ▶ After an initial more frequent use of the online communication channel, created in order to keep close contact with the members and facilitate communication among them, it was only rarely used. Several attempts to revive this more informal discussion have proven unsuccessful.
- ▶ Differences within the citizen advisory board (CAB) such as varying levels of knowledge, motivation, engagement in other networks, time constraints, etc., resulted in asymmetries, which in turn created some tension in the group.
- ▶ Managing the CAB members' expectation of the project outcomes and familiarising them with the scientific procedures proved to be a challenge. Despite their motivation to participate being quite high, they are at the same time hoping for immediate results.
- ▶ Managing the degrees of liberty concerning the project mentoring by the CAB, and clearly defining and communicating the role of the CAB. Even though the roles and the tasks of the CAB were laid out on several occasions in presentations and handouts, some projects and advisory board members were still not sure about how they should collaborate.
- ▶ Consolidating diverging opinions between representatives of the projects and members of the CAB, and preventing the impression that there was a certain level of disruption in the usual project dynamics due to the involvement of the CAB, was considered difficult.
- ▶ While CAB members were compensated for their participation in activities and received additional reimbursement for care expenses arising in the process, due to usual administrative procedures, transfer of these payments sometimes took longer than what would have been expected. This affected the most socio-economically vulnerable members in particular.

- ▶ While travel costs, accommodation and a fixed allowance for participation and care could be compensated, travelling time was not covered by the RFO. Furthermore, the travelling time itself was too long for some CAB members.

Drivers

Despite the differences between their pilots, the RFO partners were able to identify several shared drivers of participation. First, several pilots highlighted the importance of defining the process and goals from the beginning, allowing for flexible re-adjustments based on each step's learnings. This approach ensured clarity of scope and objectives as well as adaptability. Similarly, assessing available financial and human resources was deemed essential for determining the scope and feasibility of the pilot by all pilot partners. Furthermore, establishing a core team with defined roles helped in managing tasks and ensuring buy-in from within the organisation from the very beginning. Regarding the engagement activities, another common aspect which enabled a successful process was the use of professional facilitators which aided in time management, maintaining focus on key topics, and handling different perspectives. Anticipating conflicts of interest and ensuring an ethically sound process overall was another contributing factor for maintaining equity and inclusivity in the processes. Several pilots also highlighted the exchange with their colleagues in the consortium leading similar pilots as very inspiring and valuable, and the use of the ethics framework and guidelines as helpful in managing ethical questions arising from the processes. Finally, it was important for some pilots leveraging local citizen participation experts to enhance the preparation and implementation phases. The pilots that aimed to involve a wide range of participants saw this an opportunity as well to bring in fresh perspectives and further enrich their process.

In specific, the RFO partners of PRO-Ethics outlined the following drivers identified in the implementation of their respective pilot.

CDTI

- ▶ Setting up the core implementing evaluation team with clear roles and tasks in the process.
- ▶ Establishing the evaluation process according to the initially defined logic model. The pilot team had clarity regarding the scope and goals of the process from the start, while adjusting their plan in an iterative approach based on the learnings of each step.
- ▶ Anticipating enough time to recruit and engage the external support. Furthermore, the open call for tenders had to be written within official administrative procedures, containing also terms of reference which forced the team to clearly outline the necessary resources and allowed for flexibility for the pilot implementation.
- ▶ For the workshop activities, support from professional facilitators responsible for time management and keeping the focus on the topics of interest, extracting relevant input while allowing for contrasting and complementary visions.
- ▶ Anticipating potential conflicts of interest, which was especially pertinent in this pilot as CDTI was involving project beneficiaries in their process.
- ▶ Incorporating stakeholders out of the traditional scope of the programme. They provided a broader perspective on the programme's goals and processes and contributed in a decisive way to the definition of the evaluation questions, especially those related to social impact.
- ▶ Informed consent procedures and the guidelines helped to make clearer the context of participation and the relevance of ethical aspects, promoting transparency and trustful collaborative relationships.

- ▶ Applying the learnings from every activity carried out within the PRO-Ethics consortium from a quite pragmatic approach.

FFG

- ▶ Securing sufficient funding and commitment for implementing the call.
- ▶ Following an iterative approach, taking aboard feedback given by various experts, including project partners and the PRO-Ethics advisory board.
- ▶ Creating a narrative (ethically sound and practically feasible) to describe the process, methodology, goals, and impact of the pilot in a compelling manner and secure buy-in from decision-makers.
- ▶ The ethics framework was a useful tool in providing guidance regarding what ethical issues might arise and need to be considered.
- ▶ While the sample of survey respondents were not representative of the population, they were highly motivated and answered open questions comprehensively. Many survey respondents provided important considerations and valuable insights in a detailed manner, which were accounted for as a success in the pilot and influenced the final call definition. In the same way, although the self-selection method of participants for the workshop led to a potentially biased sample, the level of engagement was higher than anticipated and seen as positive.

Innoviris

- ▶ Working with local citizen participation experts and taking in their advice in the preparation and implementation of the pilot.
- ▶ Setting up an internal task force composed by several people with different expertise, including the programme manager, internal advisors, team leaders and policy and monitoring experts, to find a suitable design and method.
- ▶ Participation and participatory methods being at the heart of the current policy priorities.
- ▶ Interacting with the other RFOs within the consortium. In particular, this was important when tackling the question of how to define a citizen and how to manage expectations was important, as well as when defining the consultation methods and mapping the stakeholders.
- ▶ Reflecting on the ethics framework recommendations, which served as a basis for drawing the plan.

RCN

- ▶ Creating a cross-cutting project team that represents the organisation at different levels, working on an internal, national and international level, adapting the learnings from the pilot to the institutional profile.
- ▶ RCN momentum to have influence on internal procedures coinciding with the input received in the last workshop, feeding into the RCN working group on open research, research integrity and ethics, a group established to enhance RCN processes in the field.

UEFISCDI

- ▶ Analysing the financial and human resources at the organisation's disposal in order to make decisions regarding the scope of the pilot and a well-suited distribution of tasks within the implementing team.
- ▶ Learning from the partners' experience and refining the initial plans.

- ▶ The ethics framework and guidelines' recommendations to involve a wide range of citizens, based on clear and fair criteria for recruiting participants, helped decision-making on the chosen approach, especially when involving external support.

VDE/VDI-IT

- ▶ Involving all relevant stakeholders already in the conceptualisation of the process.
- ▶ Contacting multipliers, such as local CSOs, to pitch the project, build support, and ask for feedback on the best way to contact the target group. This led to clarity on possible obstacles from the start, while informing the approach to motivating stakeholders to take part in the citizen advisory panel.

Good practices

Although good practices are very case-specific, the following insights emphasise collectively the importance of considering organisational and participant constraints, having realistic expectations, choosing appropriate participation formats, prioritising clear communication, flexibility, and strategic planning. Here are the main takeaways from each organisation's experiences:

CDTI

- ▶ Keeping in mind the limitations both at the organisation, as well as at the participants' level.
- ▶ The voices of key external stakeholders should be incorporated in the evaluation of public policies. Maybe it is not feasible to engage a high number of stakeholders, but this should not be a reason to exclude them.
- ▶ Identifying key stakeholders already at the start of the process and outlining a targeted communication plan.
- ▶ Choosing the right participation format to engage the intended stakeholder community and collecting the data needed.
- ▶ Communicating clearly to all participants: they need to have a sufficient understanding of the process and what is needed from them, strengthening the relevance of input and enhancing the quality of outcomes.
- ▶ While operating with limited time and budget, a continuous adjustment of expectations and ambitions at all stages of the process is necessary for a successful implementation.

FFG

- ▶ Planning carefully when involving external stakeholders such as multipliers. Building trustful collaborations requires time and effort.
- ▶ Being flexible and open to try different approaches throughout the process. In the end, through a combination of different communication channels, FFG received enough responses.
- ▶ Ensuring on-site visibility when cooperating with external events.
- ▶ Minimising participation barriers, e.g., allowing respondents to skip questions in a questionnaire as well as not making the answer to one question a precondition for accessing the next question.
- ▶ Being mindful of the timing of the launch of a survey, e.g., launching a questionnaire on climate change and health in the summer seemed to be good timing.
- ▶ An online tool is helpful to reaching out to people without being too time-consuming.

- ▶ Not setting expectations too high, e.g., in terms of representativeness of the involved group of citizens. However, surprises are possible, such as in the very high response rate to open questions.

Innoviris

- ▶ Involving key stakeholders such as politicians and other decision-makers from the very beginning and maybe even seek contractual agreements with all parties, especially political ones, detailing the plans from the beginning in order to avoid roadblocks.
- ▶ Adjusting the expectations implementers have over the process to the available time, budget, and expertise they have at their disposal. E.g., trying to achieve a representative sample might be overly ambitious.
- ▶ Finding mitigation strategies to avoid low engagement rates, e.g., offering childcare options in addition to compensation, so it is easier for parents to attend, or limiting the involvement by organising only one workshop and/or shortening the timeframe of the event.
- ▶ Finding the right timing (taking into consideration the season, holidays, academic calendars, the time of day and the project's own timeline) to launch the right campaign.

RCN

- ▶ Choosing the right engagement format(s) and being willing to adapt. For instance, one of the Hub gatherings was intended to be held in person, but because there were not enough registrations beforehand to warrant this effort, it was held online.
- ▶ Making use of a good moderators to keep a balance between different participants' interactions and providing summaries of what was being said to make sure everyone understood and registered others' inputs.
- ▶ Allowing more time for participants to discuss freely in the workshop format.
- ▶ Having a "holistic" perspective, i.e., involving internal and external stakeholders from the beginning.

UEFISCDI

- ▶ Employing experienced facilitators for workshops, since it requires skill and experience to manage group dynamics and engage all participants equally.
- ▶ Choosing the right engagement format may promote a more diverse group of participants (even if not entirely representative of the population) and being in a more informal setting (e.g., world café) may ensure an equal contribution from all participants.

VDE/VDI-IT

- ▶ Creating clarity on the scope and the extent of participant involvement at the start of the process, although this may come at the expense of flexibility for the projects and mentors.
- ▶ Setting up and communication processes, roles, and responsibilities in a transparent manner for all people involved.
- ▶ Evaluating the process after each step internally and via surveys to the participants to gain their feedback and enable necessary or beneficial adjustments.
- ▶ Reaching out to expert groups – such as local citizen/civil society organisations – to learn how to best approach vulnerable groups such as informal caregivers.

- ▶ Finding a balance where the efforts of the more engaged members are valued and utilised, while less engaged members or those with fewer resources are not overwhelmed by the complexity of the process or the workload.
- ▶ Travelling time should be accounted for when arranging in person events by, for example, coordinating meetings in a more central location to the participants.
- ▶ While promoting communication between citizen panel members, a private channel is rather suitable, without the involvement of people from the organisation.

Conclusion and final recommendations

The participatory processes conducted experimentally by the different RFOs have resulted in many valuable insights. The barriers, drivers and good practices listed above reveal to a degree the distinct characteristics of each research funding organisation: Their dependence on external funding, the prevailing political support, and the organisational culture. The institutional setting informs how receptive and prepared they are to engaging in participatory endeavours that bring about the intended positive outcomes. On the other hand, because the pilots were based within the institutions, this enabled a great degree of learning, being more aware after the pilot experiment of some of the opportunities and challenges related to participatory engagement. Resulting from the experiences of the six organisations, the following recommendations can be made:

A collaborative process is key from the start

One of the most beneficial aspects of the piloting experiences was the collaborative nature of the processes. Several members of the piloting organisations at different capacities as well as external stakeholders took part already in the conceptualisation phase of the project, contributing thus to shaping the process and its outcomes. In particular, the importance of including experts in the process was stressed, mentioning both academic experts and local citizen participation experts, wherefrom the RFOs could take in advice in the preparation and pilot phases. Furthermore, key stakeholders such as politicians and other decision-makers are pivotal to be involved at the beginning to avoid unnecessary roadblocks later on, as RFOs are inherently dependent on them. Methodologies such as interviews and focus groups were used to review and validate the structure, processes, and goals of the pilots, as well as to identify the best ways of reaching out to stakeholders. In addition, the exchange across pilots within the consortium was seen as quite rewarding throughout the project lifecycle, contributing to clarifying important ethical questions as well as to helping with different aspects of the pilots, such as stakeholder mapping, recruitment, and engagement format selection. Collaborators from various domains helped identify potential challenges and limitations early in the process helped in the management of resources, both financial and technical, which led to a more efficient use of funding and infrastructure. This allowed for better mitigation strategies to be developed and integrated into the project plans. Engaging stakeholders from the beginning created a sense of ownership and commitment as well as helped in minimising bias by involving a range of perspectives, which in turn resulted in sustained interest and support for the process throughout. These exchanges not only improved the quality and relevance of the processes but also guaranteed, by aligning with academic entities, government agencies, etc., that the results of the participatory process would be taken up.

Plan realistically (and ahead)

Because RFOs are dependent on political decision-makers (usually ministries) that provide budgets for funding programmes and co-create the R&D agenda, it is important to be pragmatic and realistic regarding the goals of the project. Participatory activities demand significant resources in terms of effort, expertise, time, and financial allocation. They need the committed involvement of individuals in charge of executing the plan and a steadfast backing from leadership, both at the policy and organisational levels. Thus, it was quite beneficial for the pilots to create a good process from the start, taking into consideration the organisation, the nature of the pilot itself and the resources at hand and then, accordingly, to determine a desirable sample of participants and the methods of recruitment and engagement. For example, trying to achieve a representative sample of participants might be overly ambitious. Some RFOs, after having a clear picture of the scope of the plan, decided early on to hire

external experts to fulfil the needs of expertise. Aligning the timeline of the participatory activities with the timeline of funding calls is also crucial, as it is important for a recruitment campaign's success to find the right timing for its launch. Likewise, involving external stakeholders such as multipliers requires planning ahead, as engaging with them requires time and effort. As such, planning participatory processes at RFOs entails being pragmatic and developing risk mitigation strategies. Foreseeing challenges and taking proactive measures is important in every step of the process. It is also crucial to bear in mind that putting the envisioned action plan into practice might not always be feasible. Thus, it becomes essential to be flexible and prepared to enact the needed changes as the implementation process evolves.

Be flexible: learn and adjust along the way

Another rewarding aspect of the piloting process was the fact the participation approaches were inductive, that is, empirically grounded, instead of a ready-made system or model to be implemented. The experiences of the pilots showed that the most effective approach was to focus on those aspects that were (perceived as) important within the organisation, and gradually refining the participatory processes based on the feedback and needs of the stakeholders. As many organisations felt, while operating with limited time and budget, a continuous adjustment of ambitions and expectations at all stages of the process was necessary for a successful implementation of the plan. Sometimes, there was need to try new approaches or even a mix to receive enough responses when reaching out to citizens, for instance. As the process unfolds, each iteration or step in the process provides an opportunity for the organisation to reflect on what has been learned from previous rounds. This reflection helps refine the process and informs future decisions, leading to greater overall learning and growth. This continuous improvement helps enhance the effectiveness, efficiency, and inclusivity of the participatory processes over time, ultimately enhancing the quality of the outcomes while fostering trust and stronger engagement. Furthermore, and from a broader perspective, the iterative process of participation helps bring people closer to science, narrowing the gap between the R&I system and society. The ethics framework and guidelines facilitated this flexible design for the pilots by being open-ended, providing room for customisation and adaptation to their specific contexts. Although participatory engagement approaches are gaining traction across society, there is no one-size-fits-all solution in the case of the RFOs, and it is important to take into account the nuances and complexities of each organisational setting and plan.

Communication is not engagement

Participatory approaches demand a higher level of engagement than communication alone can provide. While clear and honest communication throughout the process is crucial, being engaged and effectively participating goes beyond just receiving information (which might not even be well understood or make the participants feel overwhelmed). This is true for all levels of stakeholders: decision-makers, citizens and organisational actors. The lack of actual engagement of the leadership can for instance delay or even stop the process. Similarly, the lack of engagement at the organisational and participant levels can hinder the process and the quality of the outcomes. RFOs need, firstly, to make sure they grasp the challenges and requirements of the involved target groups. For instance, compensation schemes need to be set up and planned, taking into consideration the participants' needs. For instance, some may want to be financially compensated, while others would rather have some services provided. Similarly, some pilots failed in establishing digital exchange processes for their participants outside the pilot activities for not sounding out their preferences. The participants' individual circumstances (education level, emotional state, etc.), moreover, will also affect the group dynamics and need to be carefully handled

by allowing, for example, for some variety in the formats or degrees of participation, i.e., a need for more engagement activities or a combination of different ones.

Be aware of constant ethical checks throughout

A successful participatory approach must attend to constant ethical checks throughout the process. Participatory processes in the context of RFOs mean constant interaction. Therefore, several ethical issues may need to be tackled and negotiated at different stages. Management of expectations of the people involved was an ethical issue across the pilot experiments. As RFOs have a limited scope of action and impact, it is necessary to be transparent and open throughout the process, specifically, communicating clearly what the benefits are for the participants, to what extent the input will be adopted and/or if there is any influence at all on the final decision. Complex group dynamics and especially power imbalances also give rise to ethical issues, which require efforts to mitigate tensions and negotiate different levels of engagement. In the case of vulnerable groups, it is essential to be even more careful when involving them, as they might have had bad experiences with official agencies or gone through several adversities, having less time to spare and being more susceptible to be disappointed when not having their expectations met. Ethical checks help ensure that the participatory process remains fair and equitable for all participants. They prevent certain individuals or groups from having their voices overshadowed, ensuring that everyone's perspectives are taken into account. Informed consent procedures and the ethics framework and guidelines helped some RFOs make clearer the context of participation and the relevance of ethical aspects. Some RFOs also utilised external support to help them guarantee a fair and equitable process, by hiring professional facilitators to moderate discussions and/or recruitment agencies to ensure heterogenous participation.

Change of culture is long-term

One desired effect of the pilot experiments and the PRO-Ethics project as a whole is a change of culture, internally at the organisational level and externally, at the widest societal level, shaping the research agenda, improving its relevance and impact, and fostering public trust. However, these need a long period of time to unfold, extended effort, and continuous organisational uptake. The anchoring of pilots at the organisations enabled them to gain knowledge through hands-on practice, honing specific skills, and obtaining a comprehensive understanding of potential opportunities and challenges that participatory activities entail. The pilot learnings themselves may become a source of orientation and inspiration in the field. However, the pilot experiences underscore an important aspect: the accomplishment of effective organisational change and the embrace of a collaborative approach heavily rely on the support provided by the institution as well as external dependencies. Regarding the ethics framework, the pilots were essential in testing and refining the document which may be used in future participatory activities at their own organisations, disseminated to projects employing participatory methodologies, and/or in discussions on ethics of participation.

Further reading

The following PRO-Ethics deliverables complement this synthesis report:

D1.2 Paper manuscript on Participatory Practices and Ethics issues in Innovation

D1.4 PRO-Ethics ethics framework 0.1 and guidelines

D2.4 Reports on pilot II results

D3.3 Report on cross-pilot workshop activities

D3.4 Compilation of ethics narratives in real life experiences

D5.2 PRO-Ethics framework 1.0

D5.3 Practical guidelines and criteria

Furthermore, the final ethics framework and guidelines have been developed into a digital booklet:

Wiarda, M., Giannelos, K., Schuerz, S., Reber, B., Doorn, N. (2023) Ethics Framework and Guidelines for Participatory Processes in the Activities of Research Funding Organizations. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8089673>

